

CYDALIMA PERSPECTALIS (LEPIDOPTERA: CRAMBIDAE): A NEW INVASIVE PEST IN WESTERN GREECE

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Mantzoukas, S. *Cydalima perspectalis* (Lepidoptera: Crambidae): a new invasive pest in Western Greece. Summary. The study concerns the first records of the box tree moth, *Cydalima perspectalis* (Walker, 1859), in Greece, and subsequent infestations of ornamental box trees in the urban environment. The pest was found infesting plants of *Buxus sempervirens* in several private flower gardens in the urban environment of Roviata, in the prefecture of Iliia, Western Greece.

Key words: *Cydalima perspectalis*, *Buxus sempervirens*, box tree moth, invasive species, Greece, Iliia.

Манцукас, С. *Cydalima persplecalis* (Lepidoptera: Crambidae): новий інвазивний шкідник у Західній Греції. Резюме. Для самшитової вогнівки, *Cydalima perspectalis* (Walker, 1859), кілька років тому вперше зареєстрованої в Греції, відзначено подальше зараження декоративних кущів самшиту у міському середовищі. Шкідником було вражено рослини *Buxus sempervirens* у кількох приватних садах в околицях Ровіата (префектура Іліа, Західна Греція).

Ключові слова: *Cydalima persplecalis*, *Buxus sempervirens*, самшитова вогнівка, інвазивні види, Греція, Іліа.

Introduction

The box tree moth *Cydalima perspectalis* (Walker, 1859) (Lepidoptera: Crambidae), which has been spreading and establishing itself across Europe during the last decade, is an invasive species affecting box tree *Buxus* spp. in the European continent. The box tree moth was included in the alert list of the European Plant Protection Organisation (EPPO) in 2007 but was removed in 2011 because no particular action was requested by the EPPO member countries (EPPO, 2011). Nevertheless, the pest could be a serious threat for natural habitats of wild *Buxus* in Europe (Bella, 2013) and a major pest of ornamental *Buxus* in nursery production (Leuthardt et al., 2010), as well as in urban landscapes, in historical and decorative gardens and parks where these plants are highly used in the landscape design (EPPO, 2012; Seljak, 2012). The first record of the box tree moth in Greece mainland, was made by Strachinis et al. (2015).

Material and methods

In mid-April, Mr Andriopoulos found larvae of this dangerous pest in his private garden in Roviata, Iliia,

Western Greece (37.8127003°N, 21.3029994°E) (Fig. 1). The genitalia slides were examined using a MBI-3 stereoscope and images were taken with a Nikon D-90 camera.

Results and discussion

The adult of *C. perspectalis* has a wingspan of 3.5–4.0 cm, which makes it a large species among European Crambidae. Two types of adults have been described, each with a different wing colour, the white and the melanic. The white type is the most common while the melanic is less frequent. In the white type, adults have white, slightly iridescent wings with a large dark brown band on the margin and a characteristic white spot in the discoidal cell, on the forewings only (Mally & Nuss, 2010). In Roviata, adults of the white type were found (Fig. 3). Infestation symptoms include damage on the leaves of the shoot edges (Fig. 1), induced by the feeding of larvae which can leave behind nothing but leaf skeletons and the epidermis. Larvae (Fig. 2) can also attack the bark. Other infestation-associated symptoms are webbing of the branches, frass and residues of moulting such as black capsules of different sizes. Heavy infestation leads

Figs 1-3. *Cydalima perspectalis* from Roviata, Iliia: 1. Mature larva and damaged shoot of the box tree. 2. Mature larva. 3. White type adult, which is the most common. (Photos by Mr Andriopoulos).

to dry plants and their defoliation, which, combined with the subsequent attack on the bark, results in the death of the plant. Box trees with a low level of damage are often able to recover if they do not suffer from renewed attacks. Investigation of effective preventive and management methods is necessary. Buxus plant importation in European countries, such as the Netherlands, Germany and Italy has largely increased in recent years, mainly from China (EPPO, 2012). The trade of infested box trees may still be the most important dissemination pathway, as detection of early larval stages or eggs is difficult (Leuthardt et al., 2010). Campaigns to communicate the risk of displacing eggs, larvae and pupae when moving infested box trees will contribute to public awareness and slow down the dispersal of *C. perspectalis*. This also applies to naturally occurring box trees in the understories of forests in the invaded range of *C. perspectalis*. Therefore, it is important to initiate a monitoring program to identify and record natural enemies (predators, parasitoids, entomopathogens) and their biological cycle, which could be used as potential biocontrol agents against this important pest.

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